

Interview protocol

Introduction

- How do you feel about today's lesson in general?

Self-concept

- How do you feel you are doing in the English class?
- How do you feel about your progress with English in general?
 - How much progress do you think you have made since the beginning of the academic year?
 - If you have made any progress, why do you think your English has improved?
 - Are you happy with your progress in English?
 - [If yes] Why so?
 - If not, in what ways could teachers support you?
- What are you particularly good at in English?
- What do you still feel you need to work some more on?

Engagement in the English class

Stimulated recall procedures [lesson video and ESM chart]

- We will now watch some parts of the lesson, and I will ask you some questions about what was happening at that moment [showing the video-replay to student and stopping where necessary].
 - [Comparing ESM chart] At this point, you reported a change in your effort/focus/feelings about the class. Could you explain what was happening at this point? Why?
 - How would you describe your relationship with your work partners on this task?

Behavioural engagement

- Overall, to what extent did you participate in today's lesson?
- In today's lesson, were there any activities where you felt more/less involved?
 - Why?
 - Which tasks make you more willing to participate and get involved?
- What makes you really involved in the English lesson?
- How much effort did you put into each task today?
 - In which situations did you put in the most/least effort?
 - What makes you willing to invest effort in the English lesson?
- To what extent do you think that your participation in the English class has changed throughout the academic year?

Cognitive engagement

- Overall, how concentrated were you during each task today?

- Can you give me any examples from today's class when you felt very focused/unfocused?
- How does it compare to a typical English lesson?
- What makes you willing to concentrate in the English lesson?
- In which situations do you feel you have to concentrate the most in the English lesson?
- Was anything difficult in class today?
 - [If yes] How did you manage it?
 - Usually, when something is difficult in the English class, how do you manage?
 - In which situations you had to think deeply and reflect?
- To what extent do you think that your focus in the English class has changed throughout the academic year?

Emotional engagement

- Overall, how much did you enjoy the English lesson today?
 - Why?
 - How does it compare to a typical English lesson?
- Which part(s) of the lesson/tasks did you enjoy the most/least today? Why?
- Which part(s) of the lesson the lesson/which tasks did you find most/least interesting today? Why?
- Which kinds of task do you enjoy the most in the English class? Why?
- To what extent did you feel bored during today's lesson?
 - During which parts of the lesson did you feel most bored?
 - How does it compare to a typical English lesson?
 - What kinds of tasks/situations make you feel bored in English lessons?
- If you could change anything in the English class, what would it be?
 - What would be your ideal English class?
- To what extent do you think that your emotions in the English class have changed throughout the academic year?

Group/classroom dynamics in the English class

- How would you describe your relationship to peers/the teacher in today's lesson?
- How would you describe your relationship to peers/the teacher in the English class in general?
 - Is there anything you would change about your relationships with peers/the teacher?
 - How much does your teacher affect your learning in the English class?
 - How much do your peers affect your learning in the English class?
- How did your team/pair work together during each group activity today?
- Can you give me an example of something that worked well/did not work well in your group/with your task partner today?
- To what extent has the class atmosphere changed throughout the academic year?

Engagement with languages

[English - Lesson]

- How much English did you use during the lesson today?
 - How does that compare to the average lesson?
 - How did using English during the lesson make you feel?
 - How confident were you while using English during the lesson?
 - In which situations did you use more English/German?
- During the English lesson, did you think or use or draw on any other languages you know?
 - In which situations did you draw on another language?
 - Were you always using English with your peers/teacher or did you switch to another language at some point? If so, why?
 - Were you ever thinking in another language during the lesson? If so, in which situations?
 - What connections did you make to the other languages you know during the lesson?
- Have you encountered any particular language issues in the English class today (for instance, not knowing how to say something or miscommunicating)?
 - If so, how did you respond?
 - How did you feel about the difficulty level of the tasks in today's lesson?
 - When you encounter a language issue in English, how do you typically respond?
 - Do you ever think about how languages function during the English lesson?
- Have you noticed any changes about the way you use English in class across the academic year?

[English - Beyond the lesson]

- Over the past week, have you used English outside the classroom?
 - [If yes] In which situations?
 - How did you feel about using English in these situations? Can you give me some examples?
- Do you ever speak English with your family/friends? If so, in which situations?
- Do you ever use what you have learnt on social media, films, etc., in the English classroom?
- How useful are these media to learn English in your opinion?
- What kinds of connections do you make between the English you learn outside the classroom and what you learn in the English class?
- How do you think that English teachers can incorporate what you learn through social media, films, etc into the classroom?
 - Do you have any suggestions about how to do this?
- How does learning English make you feel in general?
 - Is this a language you enjoy using?
 - To what extent is learning English important to you?
 - In which situations do you enjoy using English?

[Other languages]

Do you know or use any other languages other than English?

For each language

- Over the past week, in which situations did you use this language?
 - How does it compare to a typical week?
 - Have you used this language in the English class (speaking/thinking/listening to peers, etc.)?
Or in any other class?
 - Have you used this language in school?
 - What are the rules in school about using languages other than German?
 - How do you feel about these rules?
 - Do you believe these rules are fair? Why/why not?
 - What would you change?
 - To what extent is this language acknowledged by your teacher?
 - What do you think your teachers can do to incorporate your other languages in class?
- Over the past week, how did you feel when using this language?
 - Is that how you typically feel?
 - How important is this language to you?
 - How much do you enjoy using this language?
- Over the past week, how confident did you feel using this language?
 - Overall, how confident do you feel using this language?
 - What do you find most/least challenging about using this language?
- Did you make any connections between this language and English during the lesson?
 - What kinds of connections did you make between this language and English?
 - Do you ever draw on the other languages you know during the English lesson?
- Do you make any connections between this language and other languages you know?
 - What kinds of connections do you make?
- Have you encountered any language issues while using this language over the past week?
 - If so, how did you respond?
 - When you encounter a language issue while using this language, how do you usually respond?
- Do you know any other languages?
 - [If the answer is yes, repeat questions]
- Are there any other languages you would like to learn?
 - Which ones and why so?

Attitudes towards multilingualism

- Over the past week, how did you feel about knowing multiple languages?

- In general, how does knowing multiple languages make you feel?
- To what extent do you believe it is important to know different languages?
- To what extent do you feel proud of speaking multiple languages?
- Is there any language you feel especially proud of? If so, which one?
- Have you ever experienced an event in which you felt particularly proud of knowing multiple languages?
 - Can you tell me more about this event? How did you feel about it?
- Have you ever received positive feedback about your abilities to speak multiple languages? If so, how did that make you feel?
- What do you think multilingualism means?
- Would you consider yourself as a multilingual person?
- Do you feel that knowing multiple language is an advantage or disadvantage? Why so?
 - To what extent do you believe that knowing multiple languages can help you with learning English in the classroom?
 - To what extent do you believe that knowing multiple languages can help you with your other school subjects?
 - To what extent do you believe that learning new language may compromise your knowledge of German/other L1?
- Are there any additional languages you would like to learn?
 - If so, which ones?
 - Why?
- To what extent do you think it's important to know more about your classmates' languages and cultures?
 - Would you be interested in knowing more about their languages and cultures?
 - If so, why? / If not, why not?

Engagement with school

Behavioural engagement

- Over the past week, how much effort did you put into learning during your classes/outside the class?
 - How much effort do you put in your homework?
- Over the past week, how actively did you participate in your classes across your different subjects?
 - In which kinds of lessons do you participate the most?
- How does it compare to your usual participation in class?
- To what extent do you think that your participation in class has changed throughout the academic year?

Cognitive engagement

- Over the past week, what did you find most/least challenging about learning?
 - When something is difficult in your school subjects, how do you usually manage it?
- Over the past week, in which situations did you feel you really had to concentrate in school?
 - In which situations do you usually feel unfocused?
 - When you receive feedback from your teacher, how do you typically respond?
- Do you have any particular learning strategies or technique? (to learn English/in general)
- To what extent do you think that your concentration in class has changed throughout the academic year?

Emotional engagement

- Over the past week, how did you feel about being in this school?
 - What do you look forward the most about school?
 - What do you enjoy the most/the least about school?
 - To what extent do you feel comfortable in this school?
 - What would you like to change in your school?
 - How do you feel about attending a Mittelschule specifically?
 - Do you think it would have been different in another school?
 - Is there a particular reason why you chose this school?
 - Are you happy with this choice at the moment?
- Do you enjoy learning in general?
 - If so, what do you enjoy the most? What makes you willing to learn?
 - If not, why not? What would you change about your lessons/school?
- To what extent do you think that your enjoyment of learning has changed throughout the academic year?

Ecologies

- How would you describe your relationship with your school peers in general?
 - Has anything changed since our last interview/throughout the academic year?
- How would you describe your relationship with your teachers in general?
 - Has anything changed since our last interview/throughout the academic year?
- In what ways do you feel teachers and classmates can support you in school?
 - What can teachers do in particular to support your learning in the English class and in general?
 - Has anything changed since our last interview/throughout the academic year?
- In what ways do you feel that your family supports you with your learning?
 - Has anything changed since our last interview/throughout the academic year?

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